

AC 'Cost' - My Mother

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Abstract

Woman is basically identified with the role of 'Mothering'. The term 'mother' holds woman in high esteem. But the way women are being treated is far from reality. Woman is considered sub-ordinate to man and is expected to act within certain limits that are prescribed by the society. Women, in fact, are very strong and powerful. We understand this from the great Tamil epic 'Manimegalai' where a single woman confronts numerous challenges and overcomes them successfully. The Greek epic poem 'The Odyssey' brings out the intelligence and emotional strength of Penelope, Odysseus' wife who waits for ten long years for her husband, withstanding all odds that come her way. Despite this fact, the primary duty of a woman in ancient India was to serve her husband and take care of family. Medieval India witnessed the prevalence of Sati system where a woman was burnt alive along with her dead husband. Even after the abolition of Sati during pre-independence period, the woman had to stay indoors forever after her husband's demise. It was only in the post-independence period, efforts were made to send girl children to schools and colleges. But the drop-out rate of girls is much higher when compared to boys. Women constitute 48.5% of India's population and can contribute enormously towards the development of the nation. But they are denied equal opportunities. The female literacy rate in India is 65.46% whereas male literacy rate is 82.14% (2011). As per 2014 data, Indian Army has only 3% women, Indian Air Force 8.5% and Indian Navy has 2.8% women.

The government has taken a number of initiatives for empowering its female population. The year 2001 was declared as Women's Empowerment Year by the Government of India. Women's Reservation Bill promising 33% Lok Sabha seats to women, if passed can make remarkable changes in Indian politics. This paper attempts to explore the problems and challenges encountered by women in various fields that hamper the sustainable development of India in general and women in particular.

Keywords: mother-woman, challenges, epic, empowerment, literacy rate.

"A woman is the full circle. Within her is the power to create, nurture and transform"

– Diane Mariechilss

Introduction

The status of women vary widely across different parts of world. The fact is that women do not enjoy equal status and rights with men anywhere in the world. Poverty in backward countries makes life miserable, especially for women because they are economically dependent, vulnerable and powerless. For many women, life begins

with early marriage that often ends very soon with death in childbirth. Women are discriminated in all walks of life all over the world because of the social and cultural practices prevalent in all societies.

Women play a vital role in the social, economic and cultural process sometimes directly and indirectly at other times. No society can develop without considering women's welfare. Traditionally women are associated with child-bearing and household chores. They have been ignored for long in the process of development. They are equally important as their male counterparts in the growth of a nation. But they are lagging behind economically, socially and politically. The participation of women in India in education, employment, health status, decision-making, etc. is low. Gender roles assigned by the society is one of the main obstacles in women's development. History tells us that women had been treated sub-ordinate to men at all times. Therefore, it becomes important to consider the voices and views of women. Gender equality in all spheres is a matter to be addressed. By gender equality, we don't mean to say that men and women must become almost the same. It only means that access to opportunities should not depend on gender. About half of the population in India do not get equal treatment just because they are "women". To be a woman in any society for that matter is not easy. She has to overcome innumerable difficulties and problems in her everyday life.

Objective of the study

- To understand the status of women and bring out the challenges faced by them
- To lay emphasis on the discriminations against women and the impact on the growth of the nation
- To assess the cost (sacrifices made and problems faced) of being a woman

Literature Review

V.P Shijith and T.V Sekher (Nov. 2015) in the article titled "Culture, Gender Bias and Beliefs surrounding the 'Nakusa' Girls of Maharashtra" state that there is discrimination against girl child in Maharashtra. A detailed study on the 'Nakusa' girls of Maharashtra highlights that culture and socio-economic factors play a vital role in depriving girl children in many ways.

Sharada Srinivasan (Sep. 2015) in "Between Daughter Deficit and Development Deficit-Situation of Unmarried men in a South Indian Community" predicts the consequences of daughter deficit in two ways. First, the surplus bachelor men can become the source of violence towards women. Second, women deficit could add value to them, making women more powerful in marriage negotiations.

Dr. Shobana Nelasco (2010) in her book "Status of Women in India" says that the status of women in the history of India has undergone remarkable changes and a comparative study of Indian women with the rest of the world has also been made.

S.G Kabra (2013) in his book "Abortion in India-Myth and Reality" intends to bridge the gap between the prevailing myth and facts pertaining to abortions in India. He talks about different types of abortions and their consequences on the society and the increasing imbalance in sex ratio.

Methodology

Secondary data have been collected from different books, journals, articles, magazines and online data base. Being a descriptive paper, the accessible secondary data is used intensively for research study. Different charts and graphs have been extracted from online sources.

Women and Health

The concept of woman’s health includes maternal health, childbirth, mortality, morbidity, contraception, menopause, reproductive health, etc. The health of woman is directly linked with the health of children, their future well-being and also development of the nation. Malnutrition among girls and women is very common in India because they eat last and least in the family. There are many social and cultural factors for poor nutrition apart from food scarcity and poverty. Women themselves do not prioritize their health many times. Right to health and health care is also a fundamental right under the Constitution of India. Medical and health care services are not evenly available to men and women. Our male-dominated social structure puts woman in unequal access to health services. In our society boys are always preferred over girls. Hence they get better health care and attention when they fall sick. Moreover girls receive lesser food and nutrition than boys.

Early child bearing has adverse effects on the health of women. Lack of proper spacing between children is another problem. Proper prenatal and postnatal care helps in reducing maternal morbidity and mortality. Many females lose their lives during childbirth because of lesser health care facilities. Female foeticide and infanticide are quite prevalent even today that show the devaluing of girls in our society. Even though constitution guarantees equal rights to women, they in reality are powerless. They can’t decide whom to marry. They cannot even decide on when to have children and how many children to have. They do not possess fertility and reproductive rights.

Reproductive rights are the rights of individuals to decide whether to reproduce and have reproductive health. This may include an individual’s right to plan a family, terminate a pregnancy, use contraceptives, learn about sex education in public schools and gain access to reproductive health services.

Woman must have the right over her own body and fertility. Women and girls cannot be denied their reproductive health and rights. This can hamper their lives to a great extent and in turn their families and society at large. The lives of many poor girls and women can be saved if they are made aware of sexual and reproductive rights. Abortion remains restricted and unsafe abortions which are performed by untrained practitioners illegally with faulty equipment are common in India which damage the health of women to a great extent. India has the highest number of unsafe abortions in the world according to National Rural Health Mission (NRHM). There are no adequate and equitable facilities for safe abortions. Many women die due to unsafe abortion and the number of abortion-based deaths in 2014 ranged from 22,500 to 44,000. When it comes to contraception and family planning, females are the ones who have to take up the burden. Almost 95% of sterilizations are female-tubectomy though vasectomy is cheaper and safer.

Source: WHO Bulletin, UN Population Council of India

Source: www.indiaenvironmentalportal.org.in

Women’s access to health services is affected by different factors. Women spend a lot of their time on childcare and family. Thus they have very little time to think of their own health. Moreover, botheration about travelling to clinics and the money to be spent make women reluctant to take care of their health. They are less aware of the facilities available to them. Women also suffer from mental trauma because they face discrimination in all places and at all stages. They have to leave their homes after marriage, adjust with in-laws, sometimes migrate to new places with husband, etc. They suppress all their feelings which can lead to stress. Mental well-being is closely connected with the physical health of women. It is very important to address the disparities that exist in healthcare provision for the development and growth of the nation. Gender justice can be achieved only by proper provision of health and medical services to women. There is a dire lack of specialized doctors and gynecologists as far as healthcare personnel are concerned.

Women and Education

If you educate a woman, you are educating a family. If you are educating all women, you are educating the whole world.

Women’s education remains very vital for the overall development of the nation. Educated women can guide and take better care of their children and family. They can contribute in a big way towards development of the country through their participations at home and professional fields. An educated woman has the potential to balance home and profession. Although women had access to education in ancient India, it slowed down gradually in the middle-age because of restrictions against women. Again in modern India, the scenario is getting better slowly. But women are not given equal opportunities as their male counterparts. Today every child is put into a school at the age of three or four. But in most of the rural areas, if the child is a girl and the parents are poor, there is a discussion over sending the child to school. If a couple has a son and a daughter and they cannot afford to spend for the education of both, then obviously the son gets preference over the daughter. In many parts of India, even today girls’ education is not given priority. While Kerala tops with 92.07% female literacy, Bihar scores much lesser with 51.5%. If a girl child wants to go for higher education, she needs to convince her parents, relatives, neighbours. But a boy gets approval and appreciation from the same group very easily. In India, parents are ready to spend more on daughter’s wedding than on her education. This is because of the perception that daughters would not contribute to the financial needs of the family.

We still live in a society where mother is largely held responsible for bringing up her children and taking care of the family. If women are not educated, we need to understand that we are entrusting the future generations to illiterate mothers. Even though girls are better in studies when compared to boys, the question as to who has to go to school is based on sex and not capability. There are many government schemes for educating girls and women. Beti Bachao, Beti Pado, meaning Save Daughters, Educate Daughters programme offers incentives to parents who educate their daughters. Sukanya Samridhi Yojna also gives incentives to ensure that the girls give a fillip

to female literacy rates and contribute to the emerging labour force of India. But progress can be made only when there is a change in our attitude and mindset towards the girl child. First of all, we have to stop considering the girl child to be a burden and stop thinking that household work is woman's job. Women are capable of doing almost everything and deserve much more.

Source: censusindia.gov.in/2011

The world average female literacy rate is 79.7% while in India the average rate is 65.46%. According to statistics, 63.5% female students quit school during adolescence. One of the main reasons for this high drop-out rate is the lack of toilets and other facilities in schools. Eve-teasing and harassments are very common. Girls around the world, especially India have to face huge hurdles in getting education. The traditional social stereotypes control and reduce their chances to get proper education. We can never forget Malala Yousafzai who was shot by the Talibans on her way to school for addressing the female education rights. There is gender equality in education at the primary and secondary levels to a considerable extent, however there are huge inequalities in higher education. During 2006 and 2010 only 26% of girls completed secondary education where boys comprised about 50%.

Women and Employment

Employment empowers women economically and increases their self confidence and status. The number of women entering the job market is far low when compared to men. Globally just one quarter of the senior officials or managers are women and they are paid less than men. Data shows that women invest a higher proportion of their earnings in their families and communities.

Source: www.theglobaleconomy.com

Working women face more problems than the non-working females. People's perspective towards working women are not so good and correct. People are often doubtful about the staying capacity of women in a job. Hence females are not paid enough. This belief hinders the development of a woman at all levels. In the family, woman's job gets low priority because it is believed that a woman's main task is home-making. Many women who struggle hard in playing the dual role at home and work are sometimes not given the right to control the money they earn. The burden of marriage and child bearing do not permit a woman to climb the ladder in her career. In any case, if the marriage breaks, a working woman is denied the alimony. Whether a woman is working or not, she has to face exploitation if the people around her do not have the right attitude and the exploitation is double in the case of working women. Teaching is traditionally considered as a female profession because of the stereotype that caring for children is the task of females. Most school teachers in many countries are females. But when it comes to higher positions like school principals and managing authority, men dominate.

Women and War

War is considered as a complete masculine move and females have nothing to do with it. Gender roles recognize men with soldiering and women with mothering. Though women are kept mostly absent from wars, they are the main sufferers of conflicts. At the same time they are the prime promoters of peace. Women are largely killed and abused in wars and they experience physical and psychological hardships which are more common at the borders between hostile nations. Therefore it is crucial to develop policies to stop violence, foster justice and modify conflict into chances to empower women in these places.

The turbulent relations between India and Pakistan-since the inception of the two states-have not only taken a toll on peace in the region, but are also responsible for the loss of thousands of lives. Women, here like in other conflict zones, have confronted the worst kind of human rights violation: rape, molestation, and humiliation associated with being widows and 'half-widows'. Despite India being a signatory to the United Nations (UN) Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) and the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women [CEDAW], there are no precise estimates, official or non-official, of the number of women widowed or children orphaned as a result of this conflict (Butalia 2001).

It is so disheartening to think about the lives people lead at the borders-Jammu & Kashmir. They always live under the warning of bullets, not knowing when they may have to leave homes in the midnight to save their lives. During such situations they are made to stay in camps. Women experience a lot of troubles in the camp life because of lack of privacy and space. Further lack of safe drinking water and clean washrooms worsens the living conditions for women and children. Dearth of space leads to unhealthy associations among young children resulting in disputes among families. The most catastrophic effect is on the education of children who mostly do not continue their schooling after returning to normalcy.

Fencing is another serious matter in question. It affects the lives of people at the border, especially women. People find it difficult to access their fields which are guarded by Border Security Force. They have to follow gate timings and must have identity cards to enter their own fields which prevents women from performing their jobs. The middle-aged women are confronted more with security problems than economic concerns. Living in savage conditions for long periods under the threat of strangers with absolutely no place for privateness, have put them at risk and they are very unsafe. The women cannot go out for work leaving their young children behind. Even in such odd and miserable situations it is only because of the women folk the children grow up. The burden of running families fall upon women as most men are irresponsible in the camps taking to gambling. Young girls grew up to be unassertive because they were constantly surrounded by troops which

affected their personalities very badly. The conflicts at the border had its impact on the lives of women. Young girls were not permitted to go to schools and colleges. Now changes are taking place gradually after a few women started voicing their protests.

Tribal Women

Tribal women experience violence and atrocities on a daily basis. The media has brought these issues to the limelight to a considerable extent. But still, not much is done to address these issues in an effective way. The legal mechanism for ensuring rights to women is also at the budding stage. In Jharkhand 26.2% of the population is tribal but there is not even a single special provision for Adivasi women in the state budget. The Tribal Sub-Plan allocation has led to the formation of self-help groups in about 18 districts but they are not funded properly. In 2005 the State Commission for Women (SCW) was established and in 2008 women police stations were introduced. The SCW initiated legal counselling at women's police stations in 2010, but these steps are limited to cities. Women face increased burden due to displacement projects that cause mental stress. The resettlement policies provide monetary compensation and job security to one male member, ignoring the households headed by females. Such measures put women in miserable conditions, leading to loss of livelihood. Women have to travel long distances to work and they face discrimination in labour market as most women are unskilled labourers. Women are exploited very badly at the work places. The helplessness of tribal women increase the danger of gender based aggression. These women are gang-raped and murdered on many such occasions. With the undeveloped means at the village schools tribal children do not have interest in studies. They rather prefer to earn money at the nearby brickkiln where even 6 year old children are taken for work.

Despite the 2016 amendment to the child labour (Prohibition and Regulation) Act, 1986 with stringent punishments (while making it a cognizable offense and limiting work at hazardous industries), inspectors remain non-existent on the ground and child labour continues across the country.

Trafficking is another issue most common among tribal girls and women. Young girls are trafficked and misused in various ways. They are sold as brides in women-deficient places. Some are forced into prostitution and some end up as bonded labourers. When these women appeal to the legal system for help with cases of crime and violence against them, they face a lot of problems. This fear puts them in a precarious position, thereby preventing them to voice their grievances.

Conclusion

India in the 21st century of Digitalization and Information Technology needs to accept the realities of poverty, illiteracy and unemployment, especially among women. Our society and nation can progress when women are given the right to live freely, allow them to make independent decisions and give them equal opportunity in every aspect. Failure to give proper consideration to the discriminated positions of women in society can have negative effects on the overall development of the nation. Women must be vigilant and aware of their rights because they are the present and future of India. Education can empower women, give them better economic opportunities and make them lead better lives. The participation of women in governance and decision-making is very much limited. The problems and issues concerning women can be understood and better dealt with only by women themselves. So there is a need to have more female participation in the governance machinery. The political participation of women is 18.6% which can increase to 33% if the Reservation Bill is passed.

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